

EXPRESSION AND IMPORTANCE OF UZBEK CHILDREN'S PROSE SAMPLES IN THE NATIONAL CURRICULUM.

Sultonova Gulasal Shodmonovna

BukhSPI Master of Level II

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In our education system, continuous general secondary education is the main stage, and at this stage, the ground is created for students of Uzbek to be able to communicate in their native language in everyday life, and the communicative-speech principle of teaching on the basis of this, students' ability to apply the knowledge and skills acquired in the state language in the speech process is developed. Today, the National Curriculum for general secondary schools, which is considered the main backbone of education, has been developed, and the very fact that it is called the "National Curriculum" gives us great hope. Also, the fundamental reform of the methodology of teaching the Uzbek language, especially the creation of modern textbooks that provide intensive teaching of the Uzbek language to all nationalities and peoples living in the territory of our country, has become one of the most urgent tasks of today¹.

Starting from 2021, teaching the lesson called "Mother language and reading literacy" as a subject has been started. Until 2021, mother tongue and reading were taught as separate subjects. The main part of the reading book consisted of fiction, short stories, fairy tales and poems. A new generation of textbooks was created due to the fact that artistic texts in books are considered less important in terms of forming life skills and competencies in students. The texts and poems selected for the new generation textbooks are composed of artistic, informative, and scientific-popular texts that help the student to enter the life of the society. In the previous textbooks, tasks were not allocated for the development of listening comprehension competence, but in the new one, separate tasks were selected for each topic to develop this competence. Tasks allocated for the development of reading comprehension competence were mainly focused on the information openly expressed in the text or didactic elements. Questions and assignments covering all parts of reading comprehension competence have been added to the new textbooks. In the previous mother tongue textbook, more rules and information about the grammatical structure of the Uzbek language were given. In the modern textbook, only the most necessary rules are left. In the new textbooks, great importance is attached to colorful images and interesting tasks

² Zilola Madatova Milliy o'quv dasturi: tahlillar va takliflar yoxud yomg'irdan qochib, do'lga tutildikmi? Xalq ta'limi. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim 28 / 07 / 2021

that make it easier for children to learn a new subject. The most gratifying part is that now a "Teacher's Book" has been created for teachers, and an "Exercise Book" for students.

The change of the education system taught for many years, first of all, requires a change from primary school teachers, an innovative approach to the new education system, a new approach to the teaching system. For this, teachers need to prepare themselves for this program, and then apply it to students.

What is the National Curriculum (NCU)? The Ministry of Education normative documents of general secondary education serve as a basis for the development of the curriculum and curriculum of subjects, teaching methodology and assessment.

Also, textbooks, teacher's manuals, teacher's books, student workbooks, educational and methodological materials are the basis for the development, improvement and development of educational resources (including technical and scientific resources). . It supports pedagogical practice and assessment approaches and allows for integration of all these elements².

The standard of competence and skills required in each class in terms of the four main types of speech activities acquired by teaching the language to the student: listening comprehension, speaking, reading and writing. development, in which the ability to exchange and express opinions independently in various speech situations that occur during study and work, in family and public places, to perceive the heard material, as well as to obtain information by reading written sources, to events The dynamics of acquiring communication skills in the manner of expressing one's attitude is assumed.

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